

EXPANDING VOCABULARY THROUGH READING

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Nowadays teaching English has become a very important aspect of Turkmen educational system. Large-scale reforms are implemented in the systems of national science and education. Esteemed President of the country has signed a number of important resolutions and documents connected with the improvement of the work of the educational and scientific institutions of the country. Activities in this field are successfully carried out. The development of new academic curricula and the publication of new textbooks continue in high pace. Classes in all higher schools of the country are conducted according to the updated curricula meeting the spirit of new reforms in the educational system. All these are done to stimulate our youth to conduct research works and help them to get good education in the chosen specialization.

In all of these developments, teaching English plays a very important role. However, it is still difficult for students of all levels to work with vocabulary of the English language. For this reason, exploring the theory and practice of teaching vocabulary is very important for any English teacher.

“No matter how well the student learns grammar, no matter how successfully the sounds of a foreign language are mastered, without words to express a wide range of meanings, communication in a foreign language just cannot happen in any meaningful way.” [1].

In other words, regardless of one’s knowledge of grammar and phonetics, it is impossible to express oneself properly without good knowledge of vocabulary. As mentioned previously, vocabulary updates itself and new words and expressions (slangs, jargons) are constantly augmented into the “word pool”. Therefore, the importance of vocabulary in expressing oneself and achieving understandable, clear communication cannot be overstated.

There have been periods when insufficient attention was paid to vocabulary learning. What was more, vocabulary has been changed or even deleted from many textbooks and curricula. Nowadays, however, many linguists have changed their opinion on teaching and learning vocabulary and they have realized that the knowledge of vocabulary is as important as the knowledge of grammar. Vocabulary is the most important component in learning a foreign language. Therefore, recently, more attention has been paid to teaching, learning, acquiring, storing, memorizing and recalling lexis.

Vocabulary is “the basic need” of an ESL learner. Vocabulary knowledge enables language use and thus communication. Therefore, the more vocabulary one knows, the better one can express himself in a foreign language. Moreover, vocabulary acquisition is not only a matter of foreign language; native speakers can always find something to learn from the lexicon of their language.

Another point worth mentioning here is that lexis is important at every level. What is more, at higher levels the learners are supposed to learn vocabulary for more subtle purposes, such as greater precision, to convey and evoke emotions, to suggest attitudes, to invoke interest or to appeal to the aesthetic sense.

Candlin stated that “... *the study of vocabulary is at the heart of language teaching in terms of organization of syllabuses, the evaluation of learner performance, and the provision of learning resources....*” while McCarthy claims that ‘*No matter how well the student learns*

grammar, no matter how successfully the sounds of L2 (second language learner) are mastered, without words to express a wider range of meanings, communication in L2 just cannot happen in any meaningful way.” [1]

The importance of vocabulary in second language acquisition has been stressed over and over. Unlike native speakers, second language learners (L2) go through a more conscious and demanding process of vocabulary acquisition. They experience lexical gaps, the words they read which they simply do not understand or concepts that they cannot express as clearly as they could in their first language (L1). Many learners see second language learning as essentially a matter of learning vocabulary, so they devote a great deal of time to memorizing lists of L2 words.

Vocabulary acquisition is the largest and most important task facing the language learner. Actually, when students travel, they don't carry grammar books, they carry dictionaries. In fact, Widdowsen goes as far as suggesting, “*The more one considers the matter, the more reasonable it seems to suppose that lexis is where we need to start from, the syntax needs to be put to the service of words and not the other way round.*” [2].

Briefly stated, vocabulary is too important to ignore and constitutes the basis on which language lies. It is the concretization of language, the frame to which other language elements adhere. Additionally, vocabulary is not only a list of individual words of a language but also includes the grammar and grammatical forms of the language as well as the discourse created out of the combination of the individual words or phrases. Besides, vocabulary is the most sizeable and unmanageable component in the learning of any language.

REFERENCES

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- [2]. Widdowsen. Developing Vocabulary in Context. Doubleday, 1993, p. 72